

WHAT ARE ATYPICAL BRUCELLA?

The concept of 'atypical' *Brucella* emerged around 2008 following the isolation of a *Brucella*-like organism from a human infection, eventually described as the type strain of a new species *Brucella inopinata*. Unfortunately, the use of this term has become somewhat confusing being applied to two non-overlapping groups of *Brucella* species in the literature. The first use is for genetically 'atypical' *Brucella* that sit outside a 'core' clade containing the six species classically described prior to the 1970's (*B. abortus*, *B. melitensis*, *B. suis*, *B. ovis*, *B. canis*, *B. neotomae*). These 'atypical' isolates now include strains from frogs, rodents, reptiles, fish, and occasional isolates from humans and have substantially extended the known genetic diversity of the genus. While distinct from the 'core' clade, it is important to note that they are much more closely related to these 'core' *Brucella* than to members of the genus *Ochrobactrum**, considered the closest relative of *Brucella*. The second application has been for phenotypically 'atypical' *Brucella* species (notably *B. microti* described in 2008, and *B. inopinata*) which have a much more metabolically active profile (similar to *Ochrobactrum*) than the six originally described 'classical' species.

[*Adding a further level of complexity, a publication recently proposed the reclassification of members of the genus *Ochrobactrum* as *Brucella* on the basis of genomic analysis of the wider Alphaproteobacteria (Hördt et al. , 2020).]

For simplicity use of the terms 'core' and 'non-core' *Brucella* has been suggested (Occhialini et al, 2022) based on phylogenetic analysis where 'core' *Brucella* represent the six 'classical' species plus a number of recently described species that cluster phylogenetically with these (*B. pinnipedialis* and *B. ceti* from marine mammals, *B. papionis* from baboons, and *B. microti*).

'Non-core' *Brucella* refer to those isolates that do not cluster with the core as exemplified in Figure 1, below. This includes the type strains of the species *B. inopinata* and *B. vulpis* and a growing, and relatively heterogeneous, collection of strains identified most commonly from amphibians and rodents but which have been associated with occasional human infections. A second level of classification based on biological features below the phylogenetic relationships has been suggested (Occhialini et al, 2022) although biological properties of many of the emerging strains remain poorly defined.

Current understanding of *Brucella* diversity based on the 'core'/'non-core' concept is summarised in Table 1. This lists the current validly published species as 'classical' or 'new' and indicates whether they belong to the 'core' clade. 'Non-core' species (*B. inopinata* and *B. vulpis*) are shown by - in the 'core clade' column. The table also includes examples of many isolates yet to be formally taxonomically classified, some of which are members of the 'core' clade (e.g., from bats and dogs) but which also represent many isolates that fall into the 'non-core' group.

Figure 1: Whole genome sequence based phylogenetic tree of 'core' *Brucella* species (including the 'classical' species) – represented by the top-most clade - and selected atypical ('non-core') isolates – represented by the lower clades (adapted from Whatmore & Foster, 2021).

Table 1: Currently recognised and potential *Brucella* species (adapted from Whatmore & Foster, 2021).

Species	Biovars	Major Natural Host(s)	Zoonotic	Core Clade	Reference
'Classical' Species					
<i>B. abortus</i>	1-6, 9 ^a	Bovine	++	+	Meyer & Shaw (1920)
<i>B. melitensis</i>	1-3	Ovine, Caprine	++	+	Meyer & Shaw (1920)
<i>B. suis</i>	1-5	Porcine, Leporine Rangerifine (bv 4) Rodents (bv 5)	++ (not bv 2)	+	Huddleson (1929)
<i>B. canis</i>	-	Canine	+	+	Carmichael & Bruner (1968)
<i>B. ovis</i>	-	Ovine	-	+	Buddle (1956)
<i>B. neotomae</i>	-	Desert Wood Rat	- ^b	+	Stoenner & Lackman (1957)
'New' species					
<i>B. ceti</i>	-	Cetacean	No evidence ^c	+	Foster et al. (2007)
<i>B. pinnipedialis</i>	-	Pinnipeds	No evidence	+	Foster et al. (2007)
<i>B. inopinata</i>	-	?	? ^d	-	Scholz et al. (2010)
<i>B. microti</i>	-	? Vole, Amphibians, Environmental, Wild Boar	No evidence	+	Scholz et al. (2008 a & b) Jay et al. (2018, 2020) Rónai et al. (2015)
<i>B. papionis</i>	-	? Baboon	No evidence	+	Whatmore et al. (2014)
<i>B. vulpis</i>	-	? Vulpine	No evidence	-	Scholz et al. (2016a)
Awaiting description/placement					
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Rodents	No evidence	-	Tiller et al. (2010a)
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Frogs/Reptile	No evidence ^e	-	Scholz et al. (2016b) Eisenberg et al. (2020)
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Bat	No evidence	+	Bai et al. (2017)
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Fish	No evidence	-	Eisenberg et al. (2017)
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Dog	No evidence	+	Guzmán-Verri et al. (2019)
<i>Brucella sp.</i>	-	Human (Thailand)	Not known	+	Whatmore et al. (2016)

a Biovar 7 suspended as type strain shown to represent a mixed culture (Garin-Bastuji et al., 2014). Biovar 8 deleted due to absence of a reference strain.

b Previously considered non-zoonotic but recent unexpected human cases in Costa Rica (Suárez-Esquivel et al., 2017).

c A particular genotype (MLSA9 ST27) has been associated with a small number of human infections (Whatmore et al., 2008).

d The single identified *B. inopinata* strain was isolated from a human infection (De et al., 2008) as were related *B. inopinata*-like strains (Tiller et al., 2010b).

e An 'amphibian' type strain was recently reported as causing a human brucellosis case (Rouzic et al., 2020).

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